

Reduction of Nitrous Acid by Ferrous and Stannous Ions

B. P. Gyani and R. K. Prasad

Reduction of nitrous acid by ferrous and stannous ions in widely changed acid concentrations has been studied potentiometrically. Ferrous ions reduce nitrous acid to the NO state and stannous ions to the N₂O state when conditions are suitable. Half the ferrous ions are lost by aerial oxidation in this titration. Starting with low concentrations of SnCl₂ (*M*/200), the nitrite requirement is less than that expected for reduction to N₂O.

The nitrogen in nitrous acid may be reduced in a variety of ways. Some reducing agents produce NO, so that the oxidation state is reduced from 3 to 2. Some others may reduce it to N₂O (oxidation state 1) and even hydroxylamine (-2), or perhaps ammonia (-3). Latimer¹ states that one-electron reducing agents, e.g. Fe(II), reduce the acid to NO, whereas two-electron reducing agents, e.g. Sn(II), reduce it to N₂O and even to NH₂OH in cold solutions. On the other hand, Britton² reports that HI can reduce HNO₂ to N₂O:

provided that the experimental conditions are suitably adjusted. HI is a single-electron reducer:

In these circumstances it appeared worthwhile to study the reductions by Fe(II) and Sn(II) afresh under varying conditions.

The reduction of HNO₂ by Fe(II) has been reported earlier by Fisher *et al.*³ who explained their results with the help of the reaction:

According to Baudisch and Meyer⁴, nitrites may be reduced quantitatively by ferrous hydroxide in alkaline or neutral solutions, but an excess of Fe(OH)₂ is necessary. Falciola⁵ reported that the reduction of one part nitrite in million parts of water was easily observed by development of an orange colour when to the acidified solution excess thiocyanate and ferrous sulphate were added. The reduction is slower in weaker nitrite solutions. Schoer⁶ studied the kinetics of reduction by Fe(II) and suggested that the substance reduced was NO₂, produced as:

Among the earlier reports on the action of SnCl₂ on HNO₂ is that of Raschig⁷. The reaction was found to be slow and complicated, the products being H₂N₂O₄, nitrous oxide,

1. "Oxidation Potentials", 2nd ed., Prentice-Hall, N. Y., p. 94.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3892.
3. *Atti. Acad. Lincei*, 1889, *ii*, 5, 171.
4. *Biochem. Z.*, 1920, 107, 1.
5. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, 176A, 20.
6. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1926, 155, 225.

hydroxylamine, and ammonia. The reaction for these reasons has no analytical significance. Dumreicher⁸ reported N_2O to be the only product of reductions. Raschig⁹ found about 90% nitrous oxide and 10% hyponitrous acid and hydroxylamine in the reduction of nitrite by $SnCl_2$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reduction by Fe(II)

$M/100$ -Ferrous ammonium sulphate solutions in (i) $M/50-H_2SO_4$, (ii) $M/50-HCl$, and (iii) $M/50$ acetic acid were prepared. An aliquot of 20 ml of the solution was taken in the cell and titrated with $M/10$ sodium nitrite solution in a semimicro burette, using a bright platinum foil electrode¹⁰. The desired concentration of H_2SO_4 etc. was produced by adding the required amount before titration. The standard potential of the couple:

is about 1.2 volt. Oxidation potentials in many oxidations are smaller. Hence a possibility exists in these cases of direct oxidation by atmospheric oxygen in presence of hydrogen ions. Such a possibility is offset in many cases by the very slow rate of oxidation, so that a rigorous exclusion of air is not necessary. In others, it was found that exclusion of air led to altogether different results. This exclusion was ensured by constantly bubbling CO_2 .

The concentration of H_2SO_4 and other external acids added to provide primarily the H^+ ions varied in these titrations from $M/50$ (no external acid) to 8-10*N*. The results are summarised in Tables I to VI and in Fig. 1 and 2.

TABLE I

$M/100 Fe^{2+} + 20$ ml of x (*N*) H_2SO_4 (20 ml each) in the cell.
0.1*M*- $NaNO_2$ in burette. Medium = air.

	Infection.	Mole nitrite / mole Fe^{2+} .	Curve No.
..	Nil	..	
0.1	Inconclusive	..	
0.5	1.00	0.5	I
2.0	0.95	0.5	II
5.0	0.95	0.5	III
10.0	1.00	0.5	IV
20.0	0.95	0.5	V

8. *Sitzber. Acad. Wien*, 1880, **82**, 560.

9. *Ber.*, 1887, **25**, 584, 1158; *Annalen*, 1887, **24**, 161.

10. Cf. Gyani and Prasad, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 85.

TABLE II

V ml of $M/100 \text{ Fe}^{2+} + V \text{ ml of } x(N) \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in the cell. $0.1M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = CO_2 .

V.	V'.	x.	Infection.	Moles nitrite/ mole Fe^{2+} .	Curve No.
10	10	1	1.05	1.05	I
10	10	8	1.05	1.05	II
20	20	20	2.05	1.025	III

TABLE III

V ml of $M/100 \text{ Fe}^{2+} + V \text{ ml of } x(M) \text{ CH}_3\text{COOH}$
in the cell. $0.1M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = air.

V.	x.	Infection.	Moles nitrite/ mole Fe^{2+} .
20	0.5	1.05	0.525
20	2.0	0.95	0.475
20	6.0	1.00	0.500
20	9.0	0.95	0.475
20	1.2	0.9	0.45

TABLE IV

V ml of $M/100 \text{ Fe}^{2+} + V \text{ ml of } x(N)\text{-}$
 CH_3COOH in cell. $0.1M\text{-NaNO}_2$
in burette. Medium = CO_2 .

V.	x.	Infection.	Moles at nitrite/ mole Fe^{2+} .
20	1	2.1	1.05
20	6	2.1	1.05
20	9	2.1	1.05
20	12	1.0	1.0
10	18	1.05	1.05

TABLE V

$M/100 \text{ Fe}^{2+} + x(N) \text{ HCl}$ (20 ml each) in the cell. $0.1M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = air.

x.	Infection.	Moles of nitrite/mole Fe^{2+} .
0.5	1.00	0.5
2	0.95	0.475
12	0.90	0.45

TABLE VI

V ml $M/100 \text{ Fe}^{2+} + V \text{ ml of } x(N) \text{ HCl}$ in the cell. $0.1M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = CO_2 .

V.	x.	Infection.	Moles nitrite/mole Fe^{2+} .
20	1	1.95	0.975
10	4	0.95	0.95
20	12	1.95	0.975

Reduction by Sn(II)

Stock solutions of SnCl_2 in $2N\text{-HCl}$ of strengths $M/10$ ($f = 1.052$), $M/40$ ($f = 1.126$), and $M/200$ ($f = 1.020$) were prepared and preserved in an atmosphere of CO_2 . These solutions were standardised from time to time with a standard iodine solution. SnCl_2 solution (20 ml) was taken in the cell, the concentration of HCl adjusted by adding water or more HCl , and potentiometric titrations were performed with nitrite in semi-micro burette (bright platinum electrode). No attempt was made to repeat these titrations in air for obvious reasons. The results are recorded in Tables VII to IX and in Fig. 3.

Most of these titrations were quite fast, requiring not more than 15 minutes for equilibrium after each addition of nitrite and leading to steep inflections. Titrations of Fe(II) in acid concentrations below $N/5$ were slow, with vague inflections. We found that no reducing agent (Fe^{2+} or Sn^{2+}) was left in the cell after the inflections appeared. In Fe(II) titration, strangely enough, the time taken for equilibrium increased as the concentration of the mineral acid in the mixture was increased. No such effect was observed with Sn(II).

TABLE VII

$M/10\text{-SnCl}_2$ ($f=1.052$) + $x(N)\text{-HCl}$ (20ml each) in cell. $M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = CO_2 .

x .	Acid conc.	Inflection.	Moles nitrite/ mole Sn^{2+} .	Curve No.
.2	1 <i>N</i>	2.25	1.06	I
4	2	2.15	1.02	II
8	4	2.15	1.02	III
16	8	2.15	1.02	IV

TABLE VIII

$M/40\text{-SnCl}_2$ ($f=1.126$) + $x(N)\text{-HCl}$ (20ml each) in the cell. $M\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = CO_2 .

x .	Acid conc.	Inflection.	Moles nitrite/ mole Sn^{2+} .
1	0.5 <i>N</i>	0.50	0.888
4	2.0	0.55	0.977
8	4.0	0.60	1.060
16	8.0	0.65	1.150

TABLE IX

$M/200\text{-SnCl}_2$ ($f=1.02$) + $x(N)\text{-HCl}$ (20 ml each) in the cell. $M/10\text{-NaNO}_2$ in burette. Medium = CO_2 .

x .	Acid conc.	Inflection.	Moles nitrite/ mole Sn^{2+} .
1	0.5 <i>N</i>	0.00	0.88
4	2.0	0.00	0.88
8	4.0	0.85	0.83
16	8.0	0.75	0.73

DISCUSSION

The effect of bubbling CO_2 in Fe(II) titrations is remarkable. In presence of air two moles of Fe(II) require one mole of nitrite, whereas in a CO_2 -atmosphere, the nitrite requirement is double. All the evidences show that the nitrite is reduced to NO in both the cases. Thus, for example, the solution became brown initially on addition of nitrite, which gradually disappeared as the Fe(II) was gradually consumed. Reduction of the nitrite to N_2O is not indicated. Hence two moles Fe(II) requiring one mole nitrite cannot

be interpreted as reduction to N_2O . The only plausible explanation is that during this oxidation an intermediate is formed between $Fe(II)$ and HNO_2 , which can consume atmospheric oxygen quite rapidly. One such mechanism may be:

Equation (i) means that half the total $Fe(II)$ is oxidised by nitrous acid. A further reaction between NO and oxygen will not affect the result of our titration, which is between $Fe(II)$ and nitrite. This mechanism is satisfactory to the extent that only one-electron transfers are involved both with the oxidant and the reductant, but the inhibiting action of large concentrations of H_2SO_4 on the velocity of the overall reaction is not made clear.

0.1M Sodium nitrite (ml).
FIG. 1 (vide Table I, independent co-ordinates).

0.1M Sodium nitrite (ml).
FIG. 2 (vide Table II).

On the other hand, the general results in Tables VII, VIII, IX suggest that when $SnCl_2$ is titrated with $NaNO_2$, one mole of nitrite per mole of Sn^{2+} is consumed, *i.e.*, every nitrite ion consumes two electrons, implying a reduction to N_2O . The mechanism may be tentatively written as:

The same general results are obtained throughout the range of acid concentrations (0.4 *N* to 8 *N*-HCl) investigated, but the requirement of nitrite shows very notable variations as experimental conditions are altered. Thus in Table IX, the nitrite consumed falls to 0.75 mole per mole SnCl₂ when the initial concentration of SnCl₂ is reduced to *M*/200 and the HCl concentration is high (8*N*). This result cannot be explained by the self-destruction of HNO₂ (e.g. 3HNO₂ = HNO₃ + H₂O + 2NO), which would raise the nitrite requirement. A partial reduction of nitrite to an oxidation state lower than that in N₂O is indicated (production of hydroxylamine):

Taking a full view of all the reactions that may take place in the titration of SnCl₂ and nitrite, the following must be taken into consideration: (1) liberation of HNO₂ from the nitrite and the rate of its self-oxidation, (2) reduction of the nitrite (perhaps in the form of HNO₂) to N₂O and the rate of reduction, (3) reduction of the nitrite to hydroxylamine and the rate of reduction. The ideal ratio of SnCl₂: nitrite under (2) would be 1:1, whereas under (3) it would be 1:0.5. If part of the nitrous acid were autoxidised, a little more than one mole nitrite will be required under (2) and a little more than 0.5 mole under (3).

Table VII

M/l Sodium nitrite (ml).

FIG. 3

Bearing these considerations in mind, we should conclude that under conditions set out in Table VII, the reaction is almost entirely governed by (2). In presence of a high average

concentration of SnCl_2 ($M/20$) the reduction to N_2O is rapid enough to prevent autoxidation of the HNO_2 , and there is little reduction to hydroxylamine. There is of course the possibility that the positive and negative deviations cancel each other, producing an apparent 1:1 ratio.

In an average concentration of $\text{SnCl}_2 = M/80$ (Table VIII), the ratios are quite variable. In low HCl concentrations, considerable reduction to hydroxylamine is indicated; at $4N\text{-HCl}$, the reduction may be almost entirely to N_2O .

When the average concentration of SnCl_2 is $M/400$ (Table IX), it seems that reduction to N_2O is too slow to compete with the reduction to NH_2OH , which itself is very much slowed down, leading to enough self-destruction of the liberated HNO_2 . Since under ideal conditions one-third of the HNO_2 is so lost, in order to provide half mole nitrite for reduction to hydroxylamine, one has to add really 0.75 moles, which is nearly the limiting result at the bottom of Table IX. Some of these views are confirmed by qualitative tests. Quantitative estimate of products formed deserves to be investigated and is under consideration. A reversal of these titrations means reactions in nearly neutral or feeble acidic conditions. These are not satisfactory conditions. Yet, some titrations in reverse were attempted with poor results. The reproducibility was far from satisfactory and the inflections were premature.

RANCHI COLLEGE, RANCHI
AND
L. S. COLLEGE, MUZAFFARPUR.

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